

Special Relativity from Gauss' Law, ct as Spacetime and the Behaviour of Delta Functions?

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In this note, we consider whether one may obtain the Lorentz transformation of special relativity from considerations of Gauss' law as seen in a moving frame, together with ct, x, y, z being on the same footing (spacetime variables) and the nature of the delta function representing a point charge. In particular, in the rest frame, the delta function forces a symmetric ϕ , i.e. $E = -\text{grad } \phi \rightarrow -\text{grad } \cdot \text{grad } \phi = q \epsilon_0 \text{ delta function}$. Here ϕ denotes the rest frame.

The point we wish to make is that a delta function is associated with a spherically symmetrical and not skewed ϕ . This idea carries over to a point charge as seen in a moving frame. A point in a rest frame is a point in the moving even if it is multiplied by a factor and its arguments change. Now a delta function is supposed to be associated with a symmetric, non-skewed static ϕ , thus one cannot have a skewed ϕ in the moving frame where $\phi(x-vt, y, z)$ such that $-\text{grad } \cdot \text{grad } \phi = \epsilon_0 \text{ function}(v) \text{ delta function}$. One might argue that one may have symmetric ϕ in the moving frame, but this is a problem because x, t changes in a skewed fashion if x, t is forced to have the condition $v=x/t$. In particular, $x=vg(v)t$ and $t=g(v)t$ if one has $(x=0, t)$ in the rest frame. Thus, one has a skewed position vector in the moving frame, but one must use this in a function and associate it with a delta function.

In order to allow for a skewed ϕ , one must change $-\text{grad } \cdot \text{grad}$. Treating x, y, z and ct as spacetime variables means one is forced to have: $-\text{grad } \cdot \text{grad} + 1/(cc) d/dt d/dt \text{ partial}$ acting on ϕ to produce a delta function. (we explain later why we use the $+/-$ form.) This dictates the form of the skewness, we argue to:

$X, y, z \rightarrow g(x-vt), y, z$ where $g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, which is essentially the Lorentz transformation.

One also sees that $\phi \rightarrow \text{function}(v) \phi$ and $\text{delta} \rightarrow \text{function}(v) \text{ delta}$ so these show signs of transforming in a certain manner as well. In other words, the delta function dictates the functional form of ϕ in the rest frame (spherical) and also the form in the moving frame, hence dictating the transformation. One may take this one step further and note that $E = -\text{grad } \phi$ in the rest frame, but should be $-\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt \text{ partial}$ in the moving frame if the vector E is to depend on $(x-vt, y, z)$ and not on $(g(x-vt), y, z)$ as already argued in previous notes. This dictates the form of A and shows that $\phi \rightarrow \text{function}(v), A$. This information we argue seems to be sufficient to obtain the Lorentz transformation.

The Importance of the Delta Function for Gauss' Law

Gauss' Law in a rest frame is:

$\text{Grad} \cdot E = \epsilon_0 \text{ charge density}(x, y, z)$ ((1)) Here ϕ denotes the rest frame

Writing: $E = -\text{grad } \phi$ because $F=q E$ in the rest frame, the delta function dictates the form of ϕ to be:

$$-\text{Grad}'' \cdot \text{grad}'' \phi'' = \epsilon_0 q \delta'' \quad ((2a))$$

$$\phi'' = q / (4 \cdot 3.14 \epsilon_0) \cdot 1 / \sqrt{(x''^2 + y''^2 + z''^2)} \quad ((2b))$$

One may see that ((2)) is spherically symmetric suggesting one cannot have a skewed ϕ'' linked to a delta function which represents a point. There is a unique solution (which drops with r) for ((2a)) and this is the symmetric solution. This seems to imply that a point charge is associated with spherical symmetry. One may, however, have various point charges create a skewed charge distribution and create a skewed ϕ'' .

This property of the delta function seems to be critical in dictating the form of ϕ as seen from a frame moving at a constant $-v$.

The Delta Function and a Moving Frame

If one has a point charge as seen in a rest frame, one still has a point charge as seen from a frame moving with $-v$. This is a key point because it means one would need to write:

$$\phi \text{ (moving frame)} = \text{function}(v) \phi''(x-vt, y, z) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where function}(v) \text{ is some unknown function and } \delta''(x'', y'', z'') \rightarrow \text{function}(v) \delta(x-vt, y, z)$$

to retain spherical symmetry about the point charge dictated by the delta function. Here $x-vt$ is a Galilean transformation.

The problem with this scenario is that if one has a charge at rest at $x''=0, t''$, then from the moving frame $(-v)$, the charge is moving with a speed v along the x -axis. Its velocity $v=x/t$, so $x''=0, t'' \rightarrow x, t$. If one wishes to have a unitary matrix transformation, then:

$$\begin{vmatrix} |x| & | \\ | & | \\ | & | \\ | & | \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} |g(v) & g(v)v| & |x''=0| \\ | & | & | \\ | & | & | \\ | & | & | \end{vmatrix} \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } g(v) \text{ is unknown}$$

This does not lead to the Galilean transformation $x-vt$ associated with a spherical ϕ . Rather, one has:

$$X = g(v) vt \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad t = g(v) t'' \quad ((5b))$$

Thus x is skewed from y and z , but a delta function does not allow for a skewed r in ϕ . As a result one may no longer use:

$$-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi = \epsilon_0 q \delta(x-vt, y, z) \quad ((6))$$

One needs a more general expression to preserve the delta function now that one has a skewed (r, t) vector in the moving frame. If one considers:

$$\Phi = q/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \frac{1}{\sqrt{g^2(x-vt)^2 + y^2 + z^2}} \quad ((7))$$

then Φ is skewed. To obtain a delta function, one needs to have $\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad}$ and $(1/b^2) \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$ on the same footing. Here b is an unknown constant which allows bt to have units of length. The question is whether one should have:

$$-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} + \frac{1}{b^2} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \quad ((8a)) \quad \text{or} \quad -\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} - \frac{1}{b^2} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \quad ((8b))$$

We choose $((8a))$ for reasons we explain later (see $((15))$). Thus,

$$-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \Phi + \frac{1}{b^2} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} = q \epsilon_0 \delta \text{ function} \quad ((9))$$

This leads to: $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/b^2}$ $((10))$ and the skewed solution $((7))$.

Thus, $((4))$ becomes the Lorentz transformation, with b unknown. We have shown in a previous note (1) that one may use electromagnetism to show that $b=c$, so we do not repeat it here.

The Lorentz transformation $((4))$, as it stands, only applies to $x'', t'' \rightarrow x, t$. In the above problem we also have variables such as Φ'' , $E'' = -\text{grad}'' \Phi''$, Φ , $\delta \text{ function}$ and $\delta \text{ function}$. How do these transform as seen in the moving frame $(-v)$? We have seen that Φ'' and $\delta \text{ function}''$ transform as t'' from $((4))$. We note that one does not need to assume the form $((7))$, it is a solution of $((9))$.

$$\text{This means that } \Phi'' \rightarrow A, \Phi \quad ((11))$$

Thus, there is another piece in the moving frame, namely $A = v g(v) \Phi''$ where $\Phi = q g(v) \Phi''$.

$$\text{In the rest frame: } E'' = -\text{grad}'' \Phi'' \quad ((12))$$

Is $((12))$ the correct form for the moving frame? We have argued in previous notes that the E vector in the moving frame must have a vector portion depending on $(x-vt), y, z$ and not on $(g(v)(x-vt), y, z)$, the skewed vector. In the moving frame one observes a moving charge and measures r from its center. One does not use a skewed vector. Thus, $((12))$ cannot be the correct solution. We note that:

$$-\text{grad} \Phi = g^2(x-vt) / (g^2(x-vt)^2 + y^2 + z^2)^{1.5} \quad ((13))$$

Now $g^2 = 1/(1-v^2/c^2)$ so $((13))$ is a problem. One requires an extra piece with $-v^2/c^2$.

Such a piece follows directly from adding $-dA/dt$ to $-\text{grad} \Phi$, i.e.

$$E = -\text{grad} \Phi - dA/dt \quad ((14))$$

Thus, (x, t) and (Φ, A) transform according to the Lorentz transformation. In the rest frame, $q \Phi''$ is the potential energy of a test charge (at rest) interacting with Φ'' . Thus, $q \Phi$ is the

potential energy in the moving frame. In other words, rest energy (even potential energy) transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector. This suggests that one use: $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and not $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1+vv/cc}$. One wants more energy in the moving frame ((15)). For example, a rest mass seen moving should have more energy, not less.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a delta function description of a point charge in Gauss' law in a rest frame is critical because it dictates the form of ϕ'' to be spherical in: $-\text{grad}'' \cdot \text{grad}'' \phi'' = q \text{ eo delta function}$.

As seen from a frame moving with $-v$, one still has a point charge and must still have a delta function. If one insists on using $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi = q \text{ eo delta function}$, ϕ must be spherical. The problem is that $x''=0, t''$ transforms to $t=g(v) t''$ and $x=v g(v)t''$ for a unitary transformation because $x/t=v$. Thus, one has a skewed position vector, namely $\{ g(v) (x-vt), y, z \}$ in the moving frame.

We argue that a delta function cannot be associated with a skewed position vector in $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi = q \text{ eo delta function}$. In order to allow for the skewed r vector, one must change $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad}$. To do this, one treats x and bt on the same footing, where b is an unknown constant which allows bt to have length units. Thus, we suggest that: $(-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} + 1/(bb) d/dt d/dt) \phi = q \text{ eo delta function}$. The $-, +$ combination in $\{ \}$ is chosen for a specific reason which will be stated. This leads to $g(v)= 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$ and hence one has the Lorentz transformation for x, t . What about ϕ ? ϕ is found to be of the same form as ϕ'' except that r is now the skewed vector. This means that as a function ϕ'' transforms like t'' i.e $\phi = g(v) \phi''$. This suggests a vector A , analogous to x , i.e. $A= v g(v) \phi''$. Given that $q \phi''$ is potential energy in the rest frame, $q \phi$ is potential energy in the moving. Rest mass should transform the same way and should be more, not less, than the rest frame value, hence $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$. In (1) we show that $b=c$, the speed of light in a vacuum.

One may show that $-\text{grad} \phi$ has a vector piece depending on the skewed vector. To make it depend on $\{ (x-vt), y, z \}$ instead $E = -\text{grad} \phi - dA/dt \text{ partial}$. Thus, E does not transform through a Lorentz transformation.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R Finding the Speed of Light From Gauss' Law and Special Relativity (preprint, zenodo, 2024)